

Copper-doped cotton-like malleable electrospun bioactive glass fibers for wound healing applications

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ABSTRACT

The combination of electrospinning and sol-gel methods is attracting the interest of the scientific community for developing three-dimensional bioactive glass (BG)-based fibers. This paper reports the fabrication of cotton-like copper-doped BG fibers by combining electrospinning and sol-gel techniques. Acellular bioactivity in simulated body fluid, ion release, cell viability and scratch cell tests were performed. Results showed that copper was successfully incorporated in the fibers and Cu ions were released in limited concentration over seven days. The presence of copper delayed the mineralization of the fibers upon immersion in simulated body fluid (SBF), but it did not affect keratinocyte viability and migration. Wound closure in the scratch cell test was achieved in 48 h for all the investigated samples.

Introduction

Recently, the high number of application fields which can be covered by bioactive glass (BG) micro and nanofibers has raised the interest of the scientific community leading to the investigation of several processing methods to fabricate these fibers [1,2]. Several techniques, as for example melt spinning [3] and electrospinning (ES) [4,5], can be applied to obtain BG submicrometric or nanofibers mainly for potential applications in wound healing [6]. Such applications exploit the positive effect of the fiber morphology and their ability to stimulate angiogenesis and antibacterial properties [7,8]. Aiming at tissue engineering applications, electrospinning presents the key advantage of being capable of obtaining three-dimensional homogeneous fiber mats [2]. For obtaining BG fibers, one convenient approach is to combine electrospinning with the sol-gel method. The sol can be directly processed in the electrospinning set-up or a binder can be used to support fiber formation [2,4]. An alternative approach is to fabricate BG particles (micro and nano-sized) by sol-gel, which are then added to a polymeric solution, obtaining polymeric fibers containing BG particles [9]. Among the electrospinning parameters, the relative humidity (RH) in the electrospinning chamber is crucial to successfully produce cotton-like structures [10]. In the present work, the fabrication of electrospun Cu-doped BG fibers was investigated to obtain cotton-like, Cu-releasing malleable

structures for wound healing applications. The addition of copper was evaluated in terms of the electrospinning process optimization and considering the biological response, in particular cell migration and wound closure rate, by the scratch test.

Materials and methods

Tetraethylorthosilicate (TEOS), copper nitrate hemi(pentahydrate), nitric acid, poly(vinylbutyral) (PVB) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and calcium nitrate tetrahydrate and ethanol (EtOH) from VWR. The sol was prepared by mixing TEOS, EtOH and water with 1 M nitric acid and calcium nitrate. For the ion-doped sol, also copper nitrate was added (Table 1).

The sols were electrospun 48 h after the addition of the last precursor. For ES, the sol was fed with a flow rate of 0.6 mL/h, 15 kV was applied to the needle (21G) placed 12 cm from the target (Starter Kit, Linari Engineering srl) at 24 ± 1 °C and RH 30–39% for 8020 and 27–30% for 80Cu samples, respectively. The obtained fibers were heated at 600 °C for 3 h [10]. Fiber morphology was investigated by SEM/EDX analysis (Auriga Base, Zeiss). Average fiber diameters were determined with ImageJ [11]. BG fiber functional groups were assessed by FTIR spectrophotometer (IRAffinity-1S, Shimadzu). Sample wettability was assessed with a drop shape analyzer (DSA30, Krüss). Fiber bioactivity

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Table 1
Sols preparation: labels, nominal compositions, and precursor amounts.

Sample Label	Nominal Composition	TEOS [mL]	HNO ₃ [mL]	EtOH [mL]	Ca (NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O [g]	Cu (NO ₃) ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O [g]	H ₂ O [mL]
8020	80S20C	8.2	1.9	4.2	2.1	—	0.3
80Cu	80S18C2Cu	8.2	1.9	4.2	1.95	0.22	0.3

Fig. 1. 8020 and 80Cu fibers before and after HT. A–D: SEM micrographs, scale bar 10 μm. E: FTIR spectra. F: Ion release profiles for Si, Ca and Cu (ICP-OES) in TRIS buffer.

Fig. 2. SEM/EDX and FTIR analyses of 8020 (A) and 80Cu (B) fibers after immersion in SBF for 7 days. Scale bar 1 μm.

Fig. 3. Evolution of wound closure over the time and light microscope images of the scratch. Scale bar 200 μm .

was determined by immersion in SBF [12] at 37 °C for 1, 3, 7 days (ratio 0.5 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$). Ion release was measured from the BG fibers immersed in 5 mM TRIS buffer (pH 7.5) and analyzed by ICP-OES (Varian Vista MPX). BET specific surface area was measured by using nitrogen sorption analysis (ASAP2460, Micrometrics Instrument). Indirect cell tests were performed by using human keratinocyte cell line (HaCaT, CLS Cell Lines Service GmbH, No: 300493). Briefly, 250,000 cells were seeded in 24 multiwell plate, and after 24 h put in contact with the filtered (filter 0.22 μm) eluates from BG fibers, after 24 h of immersion in cell medium. CCK-8 (WST-8, Sigma) was performed 48 h after the eluate addition. In vitro scratch healing assay was performed with the same eluates according to the procedure described in literature [13].

Results and discussion

The composition 80S20C was selected after running preliminary tests on other compositions (70S30C, 90S10 and 100S), which were less suitable for the fabrication of cotton-like fibers. Among the tested values, 5 w/v% of PVB resulted to be the most suitable to obtain a homogeneous cotton-like structure (Fig. S1A–C). Fig. S1D highlights the relevance of the RH to regulate fiber macrostructure [2,4,10].

SEM observations (Fig. 1A–D) confirmed that homogeneous bead-free fibers were obtained for both compositions. The average fiber diameter was evaluated before and after HT, showing values between ~ 1000 and 700 nm. In literature [14], a significant reduction in average fiber diameter has been reported after HT. Such change was not observed in the present experiments, possibly due to the relatively low amount of binder.

Bands attributed to Si–O–Si and Si–OH [15], at 814–793 cm^{-1} , 1000–1070 and 480–467 cm^{-1} , were observed in all FTIR spectra (Fig. 1E). The bands centred around 3400 cm^{-1} and 1638 cm^{-1} can be assigned to O–H group vibrations (symmetric stretching and bending, respectively) [15], assuming the presence of residual solvent and water entrapped in the fibers [4]. The presence of PVB is confirmed by the bands detected at 2800–3000 cm^{-1} and 1432 cm^{-1} , which are ascribable to C–H groups.

Considering the similarity in composition for 8020 and 80Cu, the release of Si and Ca ions was comparable, and a sustained release of Cu ions was detected (Fig. 1F).

Both BG compositions showed highly hydrophilic behaviour. A qualitative illustration of the BG fiber handability and wettability is reported (video) in the S.I.

The measured SSA values were 6.5 m^2/g and 3.5 m^2/g , for 8020 and 80Cu, respectively. As previously reported by Norris et al. [10],

nanopores were not found and the SSA lower values measured in this study could be related to the different composition of the present BG fibers. After immersion in SBF, the fibers (which were amorphous, XRD results not shown here) became brittle and fiber fragments were identified. For both samples, typical cauliflower-like morphology, usually associated to hydroxycarbonate apatite (HCA) formation, was detected after 7 days (Fig. 2). Moreover, 8020 samples exhibited mineralization, developing a thick layer covering the fibers. EDX analysis confirmed the presence of Cu on 80Cu fibers after 7 days of immersion.

HCA formation on the BG fibers was confirmed by FTIR (Fig. 2), considering the bands centred at 580 cm^{-1} and 610 cm^{-1} [4]. 80Cu showed a delay in the detection of those peaks in agreement with literature [16].

The cell viability (WST-8 assay) showed comparable values for both BG compositions (values higher than 80% respect to the positive control, $p < 0.05$). Results in Fig. 3 report a progressive wound closure rate comparable ($p < 0.05$) for all analysed samples. Fibers did not show any cytotoxic effects and they did not inhibit cell migration.

Conclusions

SiO₂-CaO based electrospun fibers arranged in a cotton-like macrostructure with two different compositions were successfully obtained. Copper-doped BG fibers showed a delayed HCA formation upon immersion in SBF, respect to undoped fibers. Both compositions showed suitable cytocompatibility and positive effect on the wound closure rate, confirming their suitability for wound healing applications.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Liliana Liverani: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Supervision. **Theresa Reiter:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Kai Zheng:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Zuzana Neščáková:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Aldo R. Boccaccini:** Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mblux.2022.100133>.

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